

IDENTIFICATION OF THE SHALLOW HYDROCARBON ZONE USING TILT DERIVATIVE GRAVITY DATA AND THE WENNER-SCHLUMBERGER CONFIGURATION METHOD IN RANTAU PEREULAK AREA, EAST ACEH, ACEH PROVINCE

K. Alfaiz¹, Imaduddin², M.K. Jibrani¹, Y. Assyifa¹, Z. R. Qauwani¹, S. J. Fahira², R. R. Putra¹, N. Khaira², S. Futhra¹, A. Zahran¹

¹Department of Geophysical Engineering, ²Department of Geological Engineering, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh 23111 Indonesia

ABSTRACT

The increasing of human needs for oil and natural gas caused the exploration and production are in crucial to be carried out, especially in Aceh. Since the conflict begun between Indonesian Government and GAM, exploration activities have also begun to be rarely carried out. A well of an old oil, which was operated by a Dutch company is being neglected currently. An illegal drilling carried out by the community in Rantau Peureulak area of East Aceh has proved the potential reserves of this old oil well. The gravity method can be applied in the early stages of hydrocarbon exploration to determine the location of hydrocarbon potentials based on variations in the Earth's gravitational field. Through the gravity satellite, it found the anomaly data of free air is obtained with a value range of -31.7 - 80 mGal. Assuming the rock density in the study area is 2.67 gr / cm³, a Bouguer correction is made to obtain the gravity value by taking it into account the effect of rock mass around the measurement point. The gravity value is later going to be used to calculate the simple Bouguer anomaly value by reducing the free air anomaly value with the Bouguer correction value. The range of values resulting from the simple Bouguer anomaly in the study area ranged from - 92.6 - 51.6 mGa. Based on the results of the SRTM and Tilt Derivative overlay and geological structure showed that the research target location is a zone with a value of 1.5 mGal and there are several minor faults which are assumed to be fault lines where shallow hydrocarbons migrate to the surface. The lateral distribution of shallow hydrocarbon potential shows the presence of 4 (four) rock's layers, namely topsoil, loamy sand, muddy sand, and alluvium sediment with the distribution data of resistivity values obtained from 6 - 100 Ωm. An indication of the presence of shallow hydrocarbon fluid is found in alluvium sediment in the form of sand's layer with a resistivity value of 8 - 40 Ωm at the depth of 60 m. Analysis studies of shallow hydrocarbon potential distribution in the Rantau Pereulak area of East Aceh need to be carried out to understand the residual of potential realities from the field as a guide in determining the best scenario for field's development.

Keywords : Geoelectric, Gravity Satellite, Resistivity, Shallow Hydrocarbon, Tilt Derivative.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrocarbons which consist oil and natural gas are still the main energy sources that support human activities and interests in various aspects. The more needs, the higher the use of hydrocarbon so that hydrocarbon reserves are needed. Therefore, exploration and production activities are very important to fulfill the needs of oil and gas in Indonesia, especially in Aceh. Since the conflict begun between the Indonesian government and GAM (Free Aceh Movement) exploration activities have also begun to be rarely carried out. Many old oil wells have been abandoned after previously being operated by a Dutch company, one of which was in Peureulak, East Aceh. Most of these oil wells still have potential reserves, as evidenced by the illegal drilling of communities around the area to fill the needs of oil and natural gas in Indonesia, especially Aceh.

One of the efforts to increase oil and gas production in the Peureulak area, East Aceh is by mapping shallow hydrocarbon zones by measuring the physical parameters of rocks on the surface and

below the surface using both geophysical and geological approaches. Gravity data can be used as the main information in determining the location of 2D geoelectric measurements. Gravity is a leading method in geophysical exploration to determine the presence of hydrocarbon basins based on variations in the value of the acceleration of gravity (Erviartari & Sarkowi, 2008).

The gravity method is used as a preliminary exploration of natural resource targets below the earth's surface by describing a two-dimensional (2D) or three-dimensional (3D) profile through processing gravity field anomaly data, which is known as the Bouguer Anomaly. Based on this model, it can be interpreted as the geological structure of subsurface rock layers that are the target of research (Arif, 2016). To better represent the geological structure, Tilt Derivative Gravity can be used to obtain anomaly boundary data, so that the presence of geological structures in the form of major or minor faults can be identified (Praktik & Pertamina, 2020).

the Late Oligocene, compressional stress is released resulting in fault blocks along the weak zone formed by faults aged Early Oligocene. This uplifting makes the old sediment (Formation intervened) on structural highs where the depocenter basin or graben make room for the younger clastic sediments, the formation Bruksah/Parapat, Secanggang, and Bampo.

The transitional phase of basin evolution occurred during the Early Miocene and represents a relative tectonic quiescence. This stage is characterized mainly by forced regression and basin filling (down belumai). At the end of the Early Miocene, large ocean transgressions occurred so that the Malacca Platform and Central Horsts sank and became accommodation for the deposition of shallow marine carbonates including reefs (Peutu Formation). Belumai carbonate sedimentation continued during the accumulation of skeletal limestone and reefs around the platform. At the end of the Middle Miocene, transgression reached its maximum level, characterized by very rapid and thick sedimentation in the marine environment of the loam of the Baong Formation. The Bukit Barisan lift was active since the late Middle Miocene, and reached maximum activity in the Plio-Pleistocene. At that time, deltaic to alluvial sedimentation occurred (Keutapang and Seurula Formations).

Regional Stratigraphy

Fig 3. Regional Stratigraphic Map

The stratigraphy of the research area is generally composed of the following formations:

1. Julu Rayeu Formation

The lithology of this formation is in the form of a fine to coarse-grained sandstone and claystone with the presence of mica, wood, and mollusk fragments. The thickness of the formation can reach 550-2200 meters. This formation was deposited in a shallow marine environment.

2. Seurula Formation

The Seurula Formation is the formation that is the target zone in this study. This formation consists of sandstone, shale, and claystone. The sandstone in this formation has a coarser texture than the Keutapang Formation. This indicates that the regression phase is

still continuing at that time. The environment of deposition in the marine environment.

3. Keutapang Formation

The Keutapang Formation is composed of alternating shale lithology with claystone to siltstone and the presence of thick limestone and sandstone inserts. The thickness of this formation ranges from 404-1534 meters. The Keutapang Formation is the beginning of a regression cycle from sediments in the North Sumatra Basin that were deposited in a deltaic to the deep-sea environment during Late Miocene.

4. Baong Formation

This formation mostly has shale and sandstone lithology. The shale in this formation is characterized by light gray to dark gray and carbonate. This formation was deposited in the Bathyal environment and has a thickness of 1500-1750 meters.

Method

This study uses data sourced from the Topex Geodetic Satellite (Geosat), where the data obtained is in the form of Free Air Anomaly. Free Air Anomaly is the value of the gravitational anomaly that has been corrected for free air but has not taken into account the effect of rock mass and it is necessary to include the Bouguer correction into the calculation (Astra, 2013). The data used in this study is the Bouguer Anomaly gravity data. The research location is in the Pereulak Rantau Area, East Aceh Regency.

Gravity is one of the geophysical methods used to describe subsurface geological structures based on variations in the earth's gravitational field due to lateral density differences. One application of the gravity method is in the early stages of hydrocarbon exploration where this method is used to estimate the configuration or depth of the basement and the existence of the basin. The theoretical basis for using this gravity method is Newton's law of gravity. The theoretical basis for using the gravity method is Newton's Law, expressed in the following equation:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where:

F = Gravitational Attraction (N)

G = Gravitational Constant (6,673 x 10⁻¹¹ Nm²Kg⁻²)

m₁ = Mass of object one (kg)

m₂ = Mass of object two (kg)

r = Distance between the two masses (m)

Research using the gravity method can initially be done in three ways; namely land surface, marine, and airborne surveys. However, along with the development of technology, a method for measuring gravity data from satellites has been developed which has several advantages including it does not take much time and finances when compared to field measurements, besides it can easily expand the

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research area. Gravity Satellites can detect mineral deposits below the surface by utilizing gravity anomaly data obtained from altimetry satellites such as the Topex/Poseidon, ERS, Envisat, and Jason satellites to measure large-scale topography (Sandwell, 2009).

Bouguer correction is performed on Free Air Anomaly which is the output of gravity satellite data to get a simple Bouguer anomaly value. Through this simple Bouguer anomaly value, it is possible to determine the location of potential hydrocarbons using the Grav2dc. Software.

Non-commercial oil seeps found in the study area indicate the presence of oil and natural gas below the surface, this also means that there is a geological structure in the form of faults or fractures that become the path of migrating hydrocarbons. The structure of the fault can be analyzed using Tilt Derivative data from remote sensing or satellite gravity data. Tilt derivative is a filter to analyze the boundary layer so that it can be seen clearly from the boundary and shape of the target anomaly. In addition, the straightness of the fault can be interpreted with DEM SRTM data visualization so that it can be seen where the distribution of shallow hydrocarbons is in the area so that the geoelectric method measurement location can be determined for further surveys. The software used in data processing in this study is RES2DINV.

The resistivity geoelectric method is a geoelectrical method that studies the electrical resistivity (specific resistance) properties of rock layers within the earth. In this method, electric current is injected into the earth through two current electrodes and the potential difference is measured through two potential electrodes. From the results of current and electric potential differences, measurements can be calculated variations in resistivity values in the earth's surface layer below the measuring point (Apparao, A, 1997). In this method, many electrode configurations are known, including the Wenner configuration, the Schlumberger configuration, the Wenner-Schlumberger configuration, and the dipole-dipole configuration (Hendrajaya, L., & Arif, 1990). Each rock has different characteristics, including electrical properties. One of the rock's properties is resistivity (specific resistance) which indicates the ability of the material to conduct electric current. The greater the resistivity value of a material, the more difficult it is for the material to conduct electric current.

Table 1. The resistivity of rocks and minerals (Telford, W. M., Geldart L. P., Sheriff, 1976)

Material	Resitivity (Ωm)
Limestone	500 – 10.000
Sandstone	200 – 8.000
Shales	20 – 2.000

Sand	1 – 1.000
Clay	1 -100
Marl	10 - 108
Silt	10 – 200
Ground Water	0.5 -300
Dry Gravel	600 – 10.000
Alluvium	10 – 800
Gravel	100 – 600

In geoelectricity, the measured resistivity is apparent resistivity (ρ_a) (Reynolds, 1997). The apparent resistivity is:

$$(\rho_a) = K \frac{\Delta V}{I} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Information :

- ρ_a = Apparent Resistivity (Ωm)
- K = Geometry Factor (m)
- ΔV = Electrode Electric Potential Difference (V)
- I = Current Value (A)

The Wenner-Schlumberger configuration is a configuration with a system of constant spacing rules with a note that the "n" factor for this configuration is the ratio of the distance between the C1-P1 or C2-P2 electrodes to the space between P1-P2. If the distance between the potential electrodes (P1 and P2) is a, then the distance between the current electrodes (C1 and C2) is 2na+a. The process of determining the resistivity uses four electrodes placed in a straight line (Priambodo, I. C., Purnomo, H., Rukmana, N., 2011).

Table 2. Geoelectric Method Tools and Materials

No	Tools	Total Unit
1.	Nainura NRD 3000	1 box
2.	Battery DC12 Volt	1 unit
3.	Current Cable	2 rolls
4.	Potential Cable	2 rolls
5.	Meter (200 meters)	2 rolls
6.	Battery Jumper Cable	1 unit
7.	Jumper Cable	2 unit
8.	Hammer	2 unit
9.	GPS (Global Positioning System)	1 unit

Result and Discussion

The satellite gravity data is used to determine locations that have a complex structure or are dominated by many faults, both major and minor faults. So later the processing results of the gravity data can be used as reference data in conducting geoelectric surveys. The reservoir in the research area is located in the Seureula Formation where hydrocarbons accumulate, but due to the presence of a minor fault structure so that the formation of pathways and hydrocarbons in the Seureula Formation will migrate again to the surface to become oil sea pages.

Based on the anomaly data obtained from the altimetry satellite, a free air anomaly map is obtained as shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that the Free Air Anomaly corresponds to the topography, the zone with high topography is indicated by the Free Air Anomaly which has a high value with a range of values ranging from 100 to 231.1 mGal. The low topography also corresponds to the low Free Air Anomaly, with the anomaly value varying from -31.7 to 80 mGal which is indicated by a dark blue to the light blue zone. The Free Air Anomaly data obtained, has not been able to fully present geological information in the research area, therefore some corrections are needed to see further the presence of the anomaly to be studied, namely the Bouguer correction.

Bouguer correction is used to correct the value of gravity which is affected by the effect of altitude by taking into account the effects of rock mass around the measurement point. Before the Bouguer correction, the rock assumption in the study area was determined, which was 2.67 gr. This assumed rock density value will be used to calculate the Bouguer correction due to the rock density around the study. After obtaining the value of gravity which is influenced by altitude due to differences in mass density in the area around the study, the gravity value is then used to calculate the value of a simple Bouguer anomaly by reducing the value of the Free Air Anomaly with the Bouguer correction value. Based on Figure 2 the range of values generated from the simple Bouguer anomaly in the study area ranges from -92.6 to 51.6 mGal.

Fig 4. (a) Free Air Anomaly Map, (b) Simple Bouguer Anomaly overlay with Geological Structure and Contours

The low simple Bouguer anomaly is characterized by a dark blue to light blue colored zone with a value range of about -92.6 to -30 mGal. Meanwhile, the high simple Bouguer anomaly is indicated by a yellow to the red zone with a value range of about -30 to 51.6 mGal. Zones that have a high simple Bouguer anomaly value may be due to the high density in the area. A simple Bouguer anomaly map can investigate the subsurface density based on the

effect of rock mass in the area of the measurement point so as to produce a gravity value that corresponds to the subsurface density. To present the geological structure better, it is necessary to process anomaly data with certain methods in order to obtain the anomalous boundary data that you want to find. Fig. 4 presents Bouguer gravity data after filtering using tilt derivative. Assuming that the fault is the boundary between geological structures, the edges of the structure or fault trace can be represented by a tilt derivative value of 0 rad. Comparison of geological fault structure and tilt derivative will conclude that processing data is well concentrated to many features along with fault structure. Tilt derivative data can clearly show the presence of geological structures, both major and minor faults. The pattern given by the tilt derivative filter indicates the presence of a positive geological structure, ranging from 0 to 1.5 mGal (Fig. 4).

Fig 5. (a) Tilt Derivative Map, (b) SRTM Overlay and Tilt Derivative and Geological Structure

In the results of the SRTM and Tilt Derivative overlays and geological structures, it can be seen that the pinned location is a zone with a value of 1.5 mGal and several minor faults are assumed to be fault lines where shallow hydrocarbons migrate to the surface. When viewed from a simple Bouguer anomaly map, zones with low-density values are indicated in blue and the average density value is -92.6 mGal -31.7 mGal and when overlaid with a geological structure map, the zone with low-density values is also visible in zones with diverse and quite complex geological structures. To determine whether these geological structures are migration paths from shallow hydrocarbons, they are overlaid again with a Tilt Derivative map so that it is found that the research target location is right on a minor fault with a fairly high Tilt Derivative value and is suspected of being a shallow hydrocarbon migration path.

After obtaining the location of the potential distribution of shallow hydrocarbons as the research target, measurements were carried out using the geoelectric method to determine the characteristics of

shallow hydrocarbons at that location. The length of the geoelectric path in this study is 330 m.

Fig 6. Interpretation of 2D Geoelectrical A-Section Track 1

In section A, it is shown that there are 4 rock layers. The first layer is topsoil mixed with clay with a resistivity value of 10-100 m at a depth of 5 m. The second layer contains clay-sand with a resistivity value of 6-10 m at a depth of 35 m. In the third layer, there is muddy sand with a resistivity value of 6 m in the depth range of 10 to 68 m. In the last layer which has a depth of 60 m, there is a layer with a resistivity value of 8 to 40 m which is indicated as an alluvium deposit. This alluvium deposit is then interpreted as a layer of sand that acts as a hydrocarbon reservoir.

Fig 7. Interpretation of 2D Geoelectrical B-Section Track 2

In section B, it is shown that there is a fault with a distance of 60 - 78 m at a depth of 10 m. There is also a small fault at a distance of 120 – 138 m. The shallowest depth in section 2 is composed of sand-clay with a depth variation of 20 m from a distance of 0 - 138 m on the line. In addition, at a distance of 138 and 330 m, sand-clay lithology was found at a depth of 9 m. Furthermore, muddy sand was obtained at a depth of 9-68 m with a resistivity value below 6 m. The sand layer which is thought to be a shallow hydrocarbon reservoir is found at a depth of 60 m and deeper. The resistivity values obtained from both paths (A and B) show low resistivity values. It seems clear that resistivity values ranging from 2-10 m may be a barrier to water in the reservoir. indicates the strong presence of reservoir fluid in the shallow hydrocarbons.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of the free air anomaly map, we obtained anomalous variations with values ranging from -31.7 to 80 mGal which are marked with dark blue to light blue zones. Sections with low simple Bouguer anomaly values are indicated by dark blue to light blue zones that range in value from -92.6 to -30 mGal. Meanwhile, zones with a high range of values are indicated by yellow to red zones which have a range of values between -30 to 51.6

mGal. In the results of the SRTM and Tilt Derivative overlays and geological structures, it can be seen that the pinned location is a zone with a value of 1.5 mGal and several minor faults are assumed to be fault lines where shallow hydrocarbons migrate to the surface. In the results of the analysis using the geoelectric method, it is shown that there are 4 (four) rock layers, namely topsoil at a depth of 5 m with a resistivity value of 10-100 m, clay sand at a depth of 35 m with a resistivity value of 6-10 m, and muddy sand at a depth of 10-100 m. 68 m with a resistivity value of 6 m, and alluvium deposits at a depth of 60 m with a resistivity value of 8 – 40 m. This alluvial deposit is interpreted as a layer of sand that acts as a shallow hydrocarbon reservoir.

REFERENCES

Apparao. A., 1997, *Developments in Geo-electrical Methods*, National Geophysical Research Institute Hyderabad (ed.).
 Blakely, R. J., 1995, *Potential Theory in Gravity and Magnetic Application*, Cambridge University Press.
 Dangdangilo, D., Bojonegoro, K., Timur, J., & Wibowo, E., 2019, *Analisa Potensi Shallow*, Jurnal Offshore, 3(2), 76–85.
 Erviantari, D., & Sarkowi, M., 2008, *Jurnal Geofisika Eksplorasi*, 2(1), 13–20.
 Hendrajaya, L., & Arif, I., 1990, *Geolistrik Tahanan Jenis*. Laboratorium Fisika Bumi, Jurusan Fisika FMIPA ITB.
 J. D. Bennet, N. R. Cameron, A. et all, Rocks, S. J. T. & R. W., 1981, *Geologic Map 1.250,000 of Aceh Timur Quadrangle, Sumatra*, Pusat Sumberdaya Geologi.
 Praktik, L. K., & Pertamina, U., 2020, *Analisis Data Magnetik di Daerah Timor Barat Menggunakan 2D Averaged Power Spectrum , Upward Continuation, dan Tilt Derivative*.
 Priambodo, I. C., Purnomo, H., Rukmana, N., & J., 2011, *Aplikasi Metoda Geolistrik Konfigurasi Wenner-Schlumberger pada Survey Gerakan Tanah di Bajawa, NTT*. VI (Bulletin Vulkanologi dan Bencana Geologi), 2.
 Sandwell, D. T. and W. H. F. S., 2009, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 114, No. B1, B01411, B01411.
 Sosromihardjo, S. P. C., 1988, *Indonesian Petroleum Association*, Proceedings of the 17th Annual Convention, 187–210.

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